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Energy Efficiency in Slew-Rate Enhanced Single-Stage OTAs for Switched-Capacitor Applications

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Abstract: Slew-rate enhancement (SRE) techniques assist the charge transfer process in OTA-based switched-capacitor circuits. Parallel-type slew-rate enhancement circuits, i.e., circuits that provide a feed-forward path external to the main OTA, are attractive solutions, since they introduce a further degree of freedom in the speed/power consumption design space without affecting other specifications regarding the main OTA. This technique lends itself to be employed jointly with advanced OTA topologies in order to compose a highly energy efficient OTA/SRE system. However, insights in design choices such as power optimization are still missing for such systems. Here we discuss system level choices with the help of a simple model. Using precise electrical simulations, we demonstrate energy savings greater than 30% for different OTA/SRE systems implemented in a standard 180-nm CMOS technology.

Keywords: energy efficiency; switched-capacitors amplifier; switched-capacitors integrator; auxiliary slew-rate enhancer; slew-rate assisted single-stage otas

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1. Introduction

The settling behaviour of Switched-Capacitor (SC) stages, as the one depicted in Figure 1a, has been conveniently described by a simplified model [1–8]. This model breaks down the charge-transfer operation in a SC stage, whether a SC amplifier or a SC integrator, into two phases, corresponding to the idealized operating regions of the OTA: slew rate and linear regions. Hence, the total settling time, t_S , is then given by two contributions t_1 (slew-rate time) and t_2 (linear time) as:

$$t_S = t_1 + t_2, \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} t_1 = (\Delta V_i(0^+) - V_{dmax}) \frac{C'_S}{I_{omax}}; \\ t_2 = \tau \cdot \ln\left(\frac{V_{dmax}}{V_{ine}}\right), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where: $\Delta V_i(0^+)$ is the initial step seen at the OTA's input due to the charge redistribution at $t = 0$, proportional to ΔV_S through the attenuation factor $C_S / [C_S + C_P + C_F C_L / (C_F + C_L)]$; I_{omax} is the OTA's maximum output current; $C'_S = (C_S + C_P)(1 + C_L / C_F) + C_L$; V_{dmax} discriminates the OTA's operation region (slew rate for $|V_i| \geq V_{dmax}$, linear for $|V_i| < V_{dmax}$), $V_{ine} = \epsilon_R \Delta V_S C_S / (C_S + C_P + C_F)$; where ϵ_R is the relative error on the output voltage step and finally $\tau = C'_S / G_m$ is the time constant in the linear transient of a single-pole OTA, being G_m the OTA's transconductance.

As shown in Figure 1a, we are interested in the case of large voltage steps which trigger the OTA to operate initially in its slewing region. This leads us to point out that both t_1 and t_2 depends on ΔV_S respectively through $\Delta V_i(0^+)$ and V_{ine} . On the other hand, Equation (1) explicitly shows how V_{dmax} , which is a design parameter, influences the settling time, both in the t_1 and the t_2 terms also. For a Class-A OTA, like the common folded-cascode (FC) OTA, V_{dmax} can be identified with the range of operation of the input

differential pair. When sized to operate in weak inversion to achieve the maximum current efficiency [9], $V_{dmax} = 2nU_T$, being n the sub-threshold slope and U_T the thermal voltage (≈ 25.7 mV at 25°C).

Figure 1b shows the relative impact of t_1 on the overall settling as a function of the input voltage step assuming the conventional FC OTA modeled from (1). For this OTA, a simple linear relationship between its G_m (weak inversion operation of input devices) and I_{omax} exists, which can be easily shown to be: $\tau I_{omax} = 2nU_T C'_S$. This fact allows us to eliminate all the transistor-level design parameters from t_1/t_S . The design space, for this particular case, can be represented as a family of curves parameterized for a given capacitive network (C_S, C_F, C_L, C_P) and the relative error ϵ_R . In Figure 1b two design cases, named "high-resolution" and "low-resolution", are shown. They correspond to the respective parameters sets in the inset table. These are typical values, mainly derived from kT/C -noise specifications, that can be found in high-resolution (≥ 16 bits) and low-resolution (12 bits or less) systems. Marginally, specific transistor-level design choices (sizing of input devices) affect C_P , but as long as C_P is sufficiently smaller than C_S , the model accuracy is not compromised. The main OTA, depending on the specific application case, follows design optimization taking into account many other aspects, such as offset, low-frequency noise. Using a parallel-type SRE, the speed/power-consumption trade-off can be targeted without affecting other design parameters.

Figure 1. SC circuit and its relevant waveforms under the charge transfer process for a stimulus of ΔV_S (a); Slew-rate time over total settling time as function input voltage step ΔV_S considering a folded-cascode OTA with input pair working in weak inversion ($V_{dmax} = 2nU_T$) (b). Colored bands correspond to voltage supply (V_{dd}) regions considering n ranging from 1.5 and 2.0, room temperature conditions. The numerical values of the circuit parameters for high-resolution and low-resolution cases are indicated in table.

In order to achieve the best signal-to-noise ratio, ΔV_S is set equal to the maximum magnitude of the input step voltage that we assume to be the supply voltage V_{dd} . Moving from one technological node to another, distinct supply voltage domains are given. In Figure 1b, the V_{dd} regions for 1.2 V, 1.8 V, 3.3 V can be associated to the 65-nm, 180-nm and 350-nm CMOS processes, respectively. As expected, the lower V_{dd} the lower is the impact of t_1 on t_S . However, even for the 1.2-V/low-resolution case t_1 is approximately the 75% of t_S , justifying the need for power-efficient circuit techniques to reduce t_1 . For example, by reducing t_1 to one third of its original value, t_S would be halved. Intuitively this t_S reduction can be translated to a design situation where t_S is maintained, but the total power consumption is scaled down. We recently proposed a capacitive-boosted slew-rate enhancer (SRE) technique fit to this purpose [10] based on Nagaraj’s SRE [11,12]. Nevertheless, a systematic study of this technique to provide clear system-level design insight is still missing.

Here we want to address this issue by analyzing the performances of the SRE technique when combined with more advanced OTA configurations, such as the recycling folded cascode (RFC) [13]. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 develops the settling-time model for power-aware system-level choices; Section 3 introduces energy metrics to evaluate the performances of different OTA/SRE systems by the means of accurate electrical simulations; Section 4 concludes this work by stating the major findings.

2. Extended Settling-Time Model

2.1. System-Level Settling Model

We recently introduced an extension of model in (1) concerning system-level parameters [10]. This model is useful to describe the settling behaviour of the SC stage in Figure 1a whether it employs a single-stage OTA, or a OTA/SRE system:

$$\frac{t_S}{t_X} = \frac{1}{k_{AB}} \left(c_1 - \frac{V_{dmax}}{\Delta V_S} \right) + \frac{1}{k_G} \frac{V_{dmax}}{\Delta V_S} \ln \left(\frac{c_2}{\epsilon_R} \frac{V_{dmax}}{\Delta V_S} \right). \quad (2)$$

The two addends in the right hand side of (2) correspond to t_1 and t_2 of (1) respectively, normalized by the time t_X . Indeed, Equation (2) descends from Equation (1), once the following identities are defined:

$$t_X = \frac{C'_S \Delta V_S}{I_{sup}}; \quad c_1 = \frac{C_S}{C_S + C_P} \left(1 - \frac{C_L}{C'_S} \right); \quad c_2 = 1 + \frac{C_F + C_P}{C_S}; \quad k_{AB} = \frac{I_{omax}}{I_{sup}}; \quad k_G = \frac{G_m V_{dmax}}{I_{sup}}. \quad (3)$$

As evident from (3), the model of (2) emphasizes the role of the quiescent current I_{sup} drawn by the circuit from the supply rail. The parameters in (2) have the following meaning:

- t_X acts as a normalizing unit for t_S taking into account system-level specifications regarding the capacitive load C'_S , the input step amplitude ΔV_S , and the current consumption I_{sup} .
- c_1 and c_2 : both parameters mainly depend on the capacitive feedback network C_S , C_F , C_L and the OTA’s input parasitic capacitance C_P .
- k_{AB} expresses the efficiency by which the OTA uses the given I_{sup} to produce its output current when operating in slew-rate region.
- k_G expresses the efficiency by which the OTA uses the given I_{sup} to produce large transconductance when operating in linear region.

By applying the following transformation:

$$\frac{t_S}{t_X} = \frac{t_S I_{sup}}{C'_S \Delta V_S} = \frac{I_{sup}}{I_X}, \quad \text{where} \quad I_X = \frac{C'_S \Delta V_S}{t_S}. \quad (4)$$

We observe that the same expression in (2) can be used to estimate the static current consumption I_{sup} needed for a given t_S , while maintaining the rest of the constraints.

The normalizing current I_X , similarly to t_X , takes into account only system-level specifications.

2.2. Model Extension to OTA/SRE Systems

Figure 2a shows a typical Fully-Differential SC integrator configuration. It is possible to demonstrate its equivalence in terms of settling time with the single-ended circuit in Figure 1a, considering voltages and currents of the single-ended model representing the total differential-mode components of the fully-differential circuit in Figure 2a. It can be easily shown that the only transformation that has to be applied regards the input capacitance of the OTA in the equivalent circuit, C_P in Figure 1a, that should be set to twice the input capacitance of the fully-differential OTA. Considering Figure 2a, the other capacitances of the circuit are simply replicated in the single-ended equivalent, i.e., $C_S = C_{S1} = C_{S2}$, $C_F = C_{F1} = C_{F2}$, $C_L = C_{L1} = C_{L2}$.

The SRE of [10] provides a parallel signal path in order to assist the OTA during the charge transfer process; its transistor-level schematic is also shown in Figure 2a. The SRE delivers non-zero output currents only during the slew rate time t_1 , while mirrors Mm1-Mm8 are ideally turned off afterwards. This behaviour is achieved thanks to the current comparison occurring at nodes A-A' and B-B' under the action of Mb1-Mb2 and Mb3-Mb4 transistors which are set to subtract a fixed amount of current I_{th} , determining the turn-on/off threshold of the SRE. For large input differential voltage ($> V_{dmax}$), the SRE provides an amount of current equal in magnitude to $I_{omax,SRE}$.

The introduction of the SRE adds a static current consumption indicated with $I_{sup,SRE} = 2I_{tail}$. Its maximum output current capability is then measured by:

$$k_{AB,SRE} = \frac{I_{omax,SRE}}{I_{sup,SRE}} = k \left(1 - \frac{I_{th}}{I_{tail}} \right), \tag{5}$$

since the SRE is statically biased by $2I_{tail}$ (bias chain not included) and, by considering a robust sizing with $I_{th} = 3I_{tail}/4$, it is capable to deliver $kI_{tail}/4$ at the output under maximum unbalanced condition. Actually, SREs with large values of k together with low I_{tail} , which would represent an optimum design choice for the SRE, show a degradation of their effectiveness. The capacitive-boosting proposed in [10] and implemented by the capacitor C_B shown in Figure 2a solves this issue and has been adopted in this work.

From the design point of view, the SRE input commutation threshold is designed to coincide with voltage V_{dmax} , that defines the boundary between the input regions where the OTA behaves in a linear and non-linear (saturated) fashion. The threshold-conditioned behaviour of the SRE is similar to that of comparator-based SC circuits introduced in [14]. Ideally, comparator-based SC circuits has a null linear settling time ($t_2 = 0$ corresponding to $V_{dmax} = 0$) making $t_S = t_1$. This condition is extremely beneficial from the power-efficiency point of view since the current drawn from the supply rail is almost entirely used to charge directly the load. In practice, the absence of virtual ground prevents comparator-based SC solutions to be used in medium/high resolution applications. In our case the SRE always operates in parallel with an OTA in order to ensure precise virtual ground settling and thus circumventing the linearity limitations typical of comparator-based SC circuits.

From the system point of view, the overall static current consumption is now composed by the OTA's contribution $I_{sup,OTA}$ and the SRE's contribution $I_{sup,SRE}$; this can be accounted for by defining the η parameter such that:

$$\eta = \frac{I_{sup,SRE}}{I_{sup,OTA}} \quad \text{and} \quad I_{sup} = I_{sup,OTA} + I_{sup,SRE} = (1 + \eta)I_{sup,OTA}. \tag{6}$$

As already stated, the settling time model in (2) is valid also for OTA/SRE system, with due attention to the expressions of k_{AB} and k_G . The former, being related to the maximum output current, is given by the combined action of the OTA and SRE, while the

latter is strictly related to the G_m of the OTA alone which is now biased by a portion of the total supply current, namely $I_{sup}/(1 + \eta)$:

$$k_{AB} = \frac{I_{omax,OTA} + I_{omax,SRE}}{I_{sup}} = \frac{k_{AB,OTA} + \eta k_{AB,SRE}}{1 + \eta}; \quad k_G = \frac{k_{G,OTA}}{1 + \eta}. \quad (7)$$

Figure 2b shows the settling time t_S and I_{sup} while increasing the k_{AB} of the OTA/SRE system for both the FC and RFC OTA topologies. Solid traces show the possible reduction in t_S/t_X or I_{sup}/I_X when using an ideal SRE (no static power) to increase the k_{AB} . A more realistic prediction is shown by the dotted traces, which account for a $\eta = 10\%$ budget. In any case, substantial benefit of the SRE action is predicted by the model. Detailed discussion on RFC vs. FC parameters (k_{AB} , k_G and V_{dmax}) is presented in the following section.

Figure 2. SC integrator with OTA/SRE combination: (a) topology of the parallel-type SRE employing capacitive boosting. (b) Plot of t_S/t_X as a function of k_{AB} for two different OTA topologies combined with an ideal (no power consumption) and real ($\eta = 10\%$) SRE. Note that different k_{AB} values correspond to different SRE design choices for the SRE. The relative settling time t_S/t_X can be converted to a relative supply current consumption I_{sup}/I_X through (4).

2.3. Model Extension to Advanced OTA Topologies

The validity of the model in (2) for advanced single-stage OTA architectures, such as RFC [13], Super-Class AB [15], VMA [16] has not been yet demonstrated. The model in (1) and hence (2) hinges on a piece-wise linear approximation of OTA's characteristic of the output differential current as function of input differential voltage, i.e., $I_{od}(V_{id})$. A hard threshold, V_{dmax} , is set between large-signal and small-signal regions. Within

the V_{dmax} range, i.e., $|V_{id}| < V_{dmax}$, the model considers the linear small-signal circuit approximation. Outside the V_{dmax} range, i.e., $|V_{id}| \geq V_{dmax}$, the model considers perfect saturation of currents to the I_{omax} value. This highly simplified model is intrinsically prone to inaccuracy [2,3] and cannot be used to fine tune any final design, for which accurate electrical simulations are still needed [17]. Nevertheless it provides a uniform and simple analytic tool useful to compare different OTAs and OTA/SRE architectures, as will be shown in the following discussion.

Here we will discuss the RFC topology [13] as exemplary case study for mapping advanced single-stage OTAs to the model in (2). Although the methodology is of general applicability, exhaustive mapping of other advanced OTA families, as those stemming from [15,16], are beyond the scope of this paper.

Figure 3a shows a conceptual schematic of folded cascode architectures formed by a current-steering core and an output section. The current-steering core is in charge to provide the differential voltage to differential current conversion and to properly bias the rest of the circuit. The output section provides low-impedance inputs for the differential current (through Mc1-Mc2) and high-impedance output of the whole OTA.

Figure 3. Fully-differential folded cascode architectures: (a) standard and current-recycling steering cores; (b) input/output characteristics.

The FC and the RFC OTAs are obtained when the current-steering core is implemented as the standard and the current-recycling core, respectively, as shown in Figure 3a. The RFC core is obtained by equally splitting the input devices to create an auxiliary current path. Thanks to the action of mirrors Mm1-Mm2 and Mm3-Mm4, both the G_m and the I_{omax} are enhanced with respect to the FC. Theoretically, in the case of $k_R = 3$, G_m is multiplied by 2 and I_{omax} is multiplied by 3. This enhancement comes without any static power penalty [13].

Considering now the piecewise approximation, since no discontinuities are present, the relationship $I_{omax} = G_m V_{dmax}$ is set for both the FC and the RFC OTA. Since in the RFC architecture I_{omax} and G_m scale differently, the V_{dmax} parameter needs to scale accordingly, i.e., $V_{dmax,RFC} = \frac{3}{2} V_{dmax,FC}$. From the circuit point of view, the wider V_{dmax} is due to the

mirrors Mm1-Mm2 and Mm3-Mm4 which provide both biasing and signal propagation, differently from what happens in the standard core where the NMOS section only provides biasing currents.

Electrical simulations confirm the theoretical behaviour as shown in Figure 3b where the $I_{od}(V_{id})$ characteristics are shown for both the FC and RFC. The inset shows the actual FC and RFC characteristics, resulting in $I_{o,max,RFC}/I_{o,max,FC} = 3.13$ and $G_{m,RFC}/G_{m,FC} = 1.97$. The main plot is normalized to the maximum output current for each topology. The relative piecewise asymptotes are also reported for comparison. The extracted V_{dmax} parameters are found to be 97.0 mV and 154.0 mV for the FC and the RFC, respectively, which are in good agreement with the expected scaling factor. The normalized I_{od} values for $V_{id} = V_{dmax}$ are 77.6% (FC) and 77.2% (RFC) indicating that the impact of non-linearities on the model prediction accuracy is very close, and that, in both cases, the analytical techniques proposed in [2,3] would be equally effective to mitigate inaccuracy.

3. Energy Efficiency of OTA/SRE Systems

The transient of the SC circuit in Figure 1a implies a quantity of charge delivered to the effective load capacitance C'_L seen at OTA's output:

$$C'_L = C_L + \frac{C_F(C_S + C_P)}{C_S + C_P + C_F}. \quad (8)$$

The magnitude of the total charge delivered from the OTA to C'_L depends on the total voltage swing at the output node, ΔV_{oL} :

$$\Delta V_{oL} = |\Delta V_o(0^+)| + (1 - \epsilon_R)|\Delta V_o(\infty)| \approx |\Delta V_o(0^+)| + |\Delta V_o(\infty)|, \quad (9)$$

where the $\Delta V_o(0^+)$ and the $\Delta V_o(\infty)$ are easily calculated from the initial charge redistribution and the asymptotic value for an ideally infinite open-loop gain OTA:

$$\Delta V_o(0^+) = \frac{C_S(C_F + C_L)}{(C_S + C_P)(C_F + C_L) + C_F C_L} \Delta V_S; \quad \Delta V_o(\infty) = -\frac{C_S}{C_F} \Delta V_S. \quad (10)$$

Under the action of the fully-differential OTA (or OTA/SRE system), the power supply delivers the charge Q_L , given by:

$$Q_L = \frac{1}{2} C'_L \Delta V_{oL}. \quad (11)$$

Note that in differential-circuits the ΔV_{oL} variation is equally distributed between the output nodes (V_{op} and V_{on} in Figure 2a) around the common mode of the OTA. For the sake of clarity, let us assume that V_{op} and V_{on} undergo a variation of $+\frac{1}{2}\Delta V_{oL}$ and $-\frac{1}{2}\Delta V_{oL}$, respectively. Discharge at V_{on} node occurs due to charge flow to the ground rail, so Q_L is only given by the charge variation at V_{op} node. This fact accounts for the 1/2 factor in (11). Finally, the energy E_L needed for the charge transfer is calculated considering (8)–(11):

$$E_L = Q_L \cdot V_{dd} = \frac{1}{2} C'_L \Delta V_{oL} \cdot V_{dd}. \quad (12)$$

It is important to observe that E_L is proportional to ΔV_S (see (10)) through a rather complex function of the capacitor network. While C_S , C_F and C_L values derive directly from system-level specifications, C_P is the result of a specific OTA design. First-hand estimation of E_L , prior any OTA design, can be done neglecting C_P in (8), (10) and asserting the condition $C_P \ll C_S$ in the aftermath.

In a system where the stochastic or pseudo-stochastic characteristics ΔV_S are known, like in a SC $\Delta\Sigma$ modulator [18], E_L can be used to estimate the energy needed for signal processing purposes, regardless of the overheads due to the employment of actual circuits. A simple electrical testbench can be employed to numerically calculate the actual energy,

E_{sup} , drawn from the supply rail by the OTA or OTA/SRE for a single transition step (ΔV_S). The normalized E_{sup}/E_L quantity may be employed as a useful indicator to optimize the OTA or OTA/SRE system tailored to its final application. In such testbench different OTA(/SRE) topologies can be tested for efficiency comparison aiding the search for power optimization among different topological solutions.

As exemplary design cases, specifications in Table 1 are assumed. We will discuss the application of the SRE technique in both a FC and RFC topologies in comparison with the FC and RFC alone aiming to fulfill the same settling speed and precision ($t_S = 15$ ns, $\epsilon_R = 100$ ppm). Regular NMOS and PMOS devices from the UMC 180-nm CMOS process under 1.8-V supply condition are assumed. The comparison methodology starts by designing a FC OTA (FC1) compliant with the specifications in Table 1. The next step is to consider the FC/SRE system, for $\eta = 10\%$, $C_B = 500$ fF and $k = 30$ which are a valid set of parameters for nearly optimum behaviour of the SRE [10]. For this configuration the FC biasing currents and its input devices are scaled to maintain the same current density in the input devices and to attain to the same settling time (FC2). A further step is to consider the RFC topology (RFC1) which embeds power-efficient class-AB behaviour. Finally, the RFC/SRE system is considered, with the correspondent current and input devices scaling (RFC2). Since the SRE is completely turned off in the last part of the settling, the noise, offset and gain properties of the original OTA are left unchanged.

Actual transistor parameters and biasing currents are also reported in Table 1. The I_{tail} current predicted by the model Equations (2), (4) and (7), together with the mirror ratios $k = 30$ for the SRE, $k_R = 3$ for the RFC and $\eta = 10\%$ are: 375 μ A for FC1, 195 μ A for FC2, 152 μ A for RFC1 and 96 μ A for RFC2. The FC-OTA parameters are $k_{AB,FC} = k_{G,FC} = 0.5$, while the RFC-OTA parameters are $k_{AB,FC} = k_{G,FC} = 1.5$, calculated applying the definitions in (3). The input devices are biased in weak inversion operation in all cases, so that $V_{dmax,FC} = 98.8$ mV and $V_{dmax,RFC} = 148.2$ mV. Note that the SRE commutation threshold has been kept around $V_{dmax,FC}$ in both cases for the sake of simplicity; further optimization can be achieved in the SRE/RFC2 design. $k_{AB,SRE}$ has been estimated from the electrical simulations, due to the lack of a proper description of the capacitive-boosting technique effects in the modeling approach. As discussed in [10], the relation (5) is valid only neglecting the turn-on and turn-off transients of the SRE circuit. The actual $k_{AB,SRE}$, calculated through electrical simulations, is found to be 41.5.

The I_{tail} estimation is quite accurate for FC1 and FC2, while the evident underestimation for RFC1 and RFC2 can be ascribed to the simplistic modeling. More specifically, it derives from the phase-margin degradation of the RFC topology due to the non-dominant pole determined by the current mirrors Mm1-Mm2 and Mm3-Mm4 (see Figure 3a). In such condition the single-pole OTA approximation used in Equation (1) is not accurate, reinforcing the need for more refined models to abstract circuit behaviour including the presence of non-dominant singularities in the OTA frequency response [8].

Table 2 lists the results from electrical simulation using Spectre/Cadence. As expected, the use of the SRE greatly enhances the E_{sup}/E_L figure of merit in both cases, i.e., FC1 vs. FC2 + SRE and RFC1 vs. RFC2 + SRE, which in the second case showed to be even more beneficial than in the first case. Interestingly, the use of the SRE coupled to the standard FC showed to surpass the efficiency performances of the RFC alone, proving to be a quite effective and versatile technique. In absolute terms, the energy reduction enabled by the SRE is 34% for both the FC and the RFC topology. The t_1/t_S has been also estimated using the model with the k_G corrected values. In the first case, a reduction of almost 1/5 is obtained, while in the second case the slew-rate time is approximately divided by three. As already mentioned, offset and noise performances are not affected by the action of the SRE, with respect to the OTAs considered individually. For this reason we do not report comparative figures in Table 2.

Table 1. Specifications and OTAs design parameters used in the testbech.

Specifications		
t_S	15	ns
ΔV_S	1.8	V
C_S	1.5	pF
C_F	6.0	pF
C_L	1.0	pF
ϵ_R	100	ppm
SRE, $I_{tail} = 20 \mu A,$ $C_B = 500$ fF.		
	L (nm)	W (μm)
Mi1-2	180	1.50
Mi3-4	180	4.50
Mm1, Mm3	180	1.62
Mm2, Mm4	180	48.60
Mm5, Mm7	180	0.54
Mm6, Mm8	180	16.20
Mtn	1000	2.88
Mtp	1000	0.96
Mb1-2	1000	2.16
Mb3-4	1000	0.72
	L (nm)	W (μm)
Mi1-2	180	480
Mm1-2	400	32
Mc1-2	180	72
Mc3-4	180	288
Mb1-2	400	73
Mt1	400	146
Mt2	180	576
	L (nm)	W (μm)
Mi1-2	180	240
Mm1-2	400	32
Mc1-2	180	72
Mc3-4	180	288
Mb1-2	400	73
Mt1	400	146
Mt2	180	576
	L (nm)	W (μm)
Mi1'-1''-2'-2''	180	156
Mm1-3	400	16
Mm2-4	400	48
Mc5-6	180	36
Mc1-2	180	72
Mc3-4	180	28
Mb1-2	400	73
Mt1	400	146
Mt2	180	72

Table 1. Cont.

Specifications		
	L (nm)	W (μm)
Mi1'-1''-2'-2''	180	78
Mm1-3	400	16
Mm2-4	400	48
Mc5-6	180	36
Mc1-2	180	72
Mc3-4	180	28
Mb1-2	400	73
Mt1	400	146
Mt2	180	72

Table 2. Electrical simulation results and impact of slew-rate time on the overall settling time (t_1/t_S)* estimated by means of the proposed model.

	FC1	FC2 + SRE	RFC1	RFC2 + SRE
t_S (ns)	14.98	14.69	14.64	14.61
E_{sup} (pJ)	21.93	14.49	15.52	10.3
C_P (fF)	701	358	528	270
E_L (pJ)	3.13	3.14	3.13	3.15
E_{sup}/E_L	7.00	4.61	4.95	3.27
$(t_1/t_S)^*$ (%)	49.8	10.5	38.8	11.9

4. Conclusions

This work discuss energy efficiency optimization by using parallel-type SRE circuits to assist single-stage OTAs in the charge transfer process. Detailed electrical simulations demonstrated that power savings greater of 30% are achieved both when using standard Class-A OTAs and more advanced OTA topologies like the recycling folded cascode topology. The optimization process is aided by a simple model useful to fairly compare different OTA topologies. Model accuracy limitations, when used to predict absolute power figures, are also discussed.

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